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Fall Risk Classification in Community-Dwelling Older Adults: A Cross-Sectional Machine Learning Study

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Abstract

Falls are a leading cause of injury and functional decline among older adults, yet existing screening tools often struggle to capture the full complexity of fall risk or reliably differentiate those at higher risk.. Through this thesis, an interpretable machine learning model was developed to classify fall risk using multimodal data collected during Denmark’s preventive home visit (PHV) program. A retrospective cross-sectional dataset of 382 community-dwelling adults aged 75+ from the HANC study was analyzed. Input features included physical performance (SPPB, grip strength), physical activity from wrist-worn accelerometry (mean counts per minute), health-related quality of life (SF-12, EQ-5D), cognition (DSST, MMSE), fatigue (Avlund Mobility-Tiredness, Pittsburgh Fatiguability Scale), activities of daily living (ADLs), and fear of falling (FES-I). The outcome was self-reported falls in the past year.

An XGBoost classifier was trained and evaluated using five-fold cross-validation with hyperparameters selected using Bayesian optimization. The model achieved moderate

discrimination (AUROC = 0.662; AUPRC = 0.473) and calibration (log-loss = 0.572; Brier score = 0.193). Using the Youden-selected threshold (≥ 0.29 to classify fallers), sensitivity was 0.64, specificity 0.60, precision 0.40, F1 score 0.49, and balanced accuracy 0.62. Overall, these results are comparable to those reported in studies using multimodal datasets of similar sample sizes and feature inputs. SHAP analysis highlighted physical activity, chair rise time, fear of falling, grip strength, and health-related quality of life as key predictors of fall risk.

The model's design aligns with Denmark's PHV framework and emphasizes transparent reporting of evaluation metrics, including calibration and threshold selection, addressing key gaps in practical decision-making and reproducibility within the fall-risk classification literature. Future research should focus on expanded datasets, temporal validation, and investigating three-tiered classification schemes, such as by including a recurrent faller group to enhance clinical utility. With further development, this approach could support scalable, data-driven fall-risk stratification within municipal public health systems, improving early identification and targeted preventive interventions for older adults.

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Introduction

Background: Impact of Falls, Frailty, and Ageing

Falls are a major public health concern among adults aged 65 and older, with a global prevalence estimated at 26.5% in a systematic review of over 36 million individuals (Salari et al., 2022).

They are the second leading cause of unintentional injury-related deaths worldwide, with approximately 37.3 million falls each year requiring medical attention (WHO, 2021). Beyond the immediate injuries, falls often lead to long-term disability, loss of independence, and reduced quality of life. The economic impact is substantial: in the United States alone, non-fatal falls among older adults accounted for an estimated \$80 billion in healthcare spending in 2020 (Haddad et al., 2024). These figures emphasize the urgent need to identify individuals at high risk before a fall occurs.

One central concept in understanding fall risk is frailty, which presents as a decline across multiple physiological systems, leaving individuals more vulnerable to adverse outcomes such as hospitalization and mortality. Fried et al. (2001) defined the “frailty phenotype” as the presence of at least three of the following characteristics: weakness, slow gait speed, low physical activity, exhaustion, and unintentional weight loss. Evidence from a systematic review of 11 studies showed that frailty nearly doubled the odds of future falls (OR = 1.84), while pre-frailty also conferred a smaller but significant increase in risk (OR = 1.25) compared with non-frail individuals (Kojima, 2015).

Moreover, the implications of frailty extend beyond falls alone; it has been associated with fractures, mobility limitations, social isolation, depression, cognitive decline, dementia, and greater likelihood of institutionalization (Hoogendijk et al., 2019). In a large cohort of 493,737

UK Biobank participants aged 37–73 years, those with at least three frailty phenotype characteristics had a two-fold increase in 7-year mortality risk and were linked to multi-morbidity, with 18% having four or more long-term conditions (Hanlon et al., 2018). This interplay between frailty, chronic conditions, and falls highlights why a broader perspective is needed when assessing fall risk.

In this study, frailty is used as a conceptual framework to illustrate the multidimensional nature of fall risk, but we do not apply a single frailty scale. Instead, we draw on a broad set of physical, cognitive, psychological, and functional measures to more comprehensively capture fall risk in older adults. Although frailty can develop at any age, it typically emerges gradually over decades, meaning that by the time it is clinically apparent, functional decline may already be well advanced (Hoogendijk et al., 2019). Therefore, early identification of at-risk individuals is essential, yet no universally accepted tool for frailty assessment exists. This lack of a global standard highlights the challenges of capturing the full, multi-factorial nature of fall risk – a gap that current screening tools also struggle to address.

Limitations of Existing Fall-Risk Screening Tools

Effective fall screening first establishing which factors should be prioritized for assessment. One review identified primary fall risk factors including impaired gait and balance, polypharmacy, and prior fall history, and secondary factors including age, female gender, visual impairments, cognitive declines, and environmental factors (Ambrose et al., 2013). Additionally, psychological factors are also key contributors to fall risk and overall vulnerability.

Fear of falling is not only common among older adults but also linked to activity restriction, reduced physical and cognitive function, and diminished quality of life. A systematic review of nearly 30,000 participants confirmed that this association was independent of actual fall history,

(Schoene et al., 2019). What results is a cycle of fear of falling, activity avoidance, social isolation, physical and cognitive impairments, and resulting further falls. This suggests that psychological factors exert their own influence on risk and should therefore be included in comprehensive assessments.

Fall risk assessment tools (FRATs) vary in type but often rely too heavily on physical measures. A systematic review of 43 FRATs found that most items treated the body as the main point of failure, while activities, participation, and especially environmental and personal factors were under-represented (De Clercq et al., 2021). This over-reliance on body function highlights why many tools fail to capture the broader, multifactorial nature of falls, a limitation also reflected in a meta-analysis showing that these commonly used FRATs have limited predictive validity (Park, 2018). For example, hospital checklists such as STRATIFY, the Hendrich II Fall Risk Model, and the Downton Fall Risk Index demonstrated high sensitivities (0.7–0.89) but poor specificities (0.26–0.6), leading to frequent false alarms. By contrast, balance-focused scales such as the Berg Balance Scale (BBS) and the Mobility Interaction Fall Chart (MIFC) showed higher specificity (up to 0.90 for BBS) but variable or low sensitivity, resulting in frequent missed fallers.

In clinical practice, one of the most used FRATs is the Timed Up and Go (TUG), valued for its speed and simplicity. However, a meta-analysis of 25 studies found that the TUG has limited ability to predict falls in community-dwelling older adults (Barry et al., 2014). At the commonly used cutoff of 13.5 seconds, its pooled specificity was moderate (0.74), sensitivity was poor (0.31), and it was not a significant predictor of falls (OR = 1.01). These findings reinforce that even widely adopted clinical tools cannot reliably stratify fall risk on their own.

Overall, current FRATs fail to capture the full complexity of falls. While some offer simplicity and ease of use, they may overlook critical predictors such as cognitive status, medication use,

comorbidity burden, and psychosocial factors. Their reliance on fixed cut-offs also limits adaptability, as thresholds that may not generalize well across populations. Combined with the frequent trade-off between sensitivity and specificity, these constraints reduce their effectiveness for scalable, preventive screening in real-world community settings – thereby creating a clear need for predictive methods that can better capture the multi-domain complexity of fall risk.

Opportunities for Data-Driven Prediction and Machine Learning

While conventional FRATs may be practical, they typically assess a single domain at a time, such as mobility or balance, limiting their ability to reflect the multifactorial nature of falls. In contrast, data-driven approaches can integrate multiple domains simultaneously and leverage large, diverse datasets to uncover patterns and interactions between risk factors that would otherwise remain hidden, thereby better capturing the real-world complexity of fall risk.

What is Machine Learning?

Machine learning (ML) is a branch of artificial intelligence that uses algorithms to detect patterns in data, without being explicitly programmed for each specific task. In supervised ML, the algorithm is trained on data where the outcome is already known – for example, whether an older adult has experienced a fall in the past year. The model then learns which combinations of predictors (such as age, strength, cognition, or physical activity) are most predictive, and applies this knowledge to new, unseen cases. A key advantage is that ML can flexibly model non-linear relationships and interactions between variables that traditional statistical approaches struggle to capture.

ML Compared with Conventional Fall Risk Assessment Tools

Several studies have already explored the use of ML in fall risk prediction by integrating information from multiple domains. A review of 19 fall risk prediction ML studies in community-dwelling older adults reported classification accuracies often exceeding 70% when distinguishing fallers from non-fallers (Capodici et al., 2025). When compared with conventional FRATs, Palumbo et al. (2016), using data from the InCHIANTI study, demonstrated that an ML model trained on over 1,000 variables achieved an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) of 0.71 for predicting future falls. In contrast, traditional FRATs such as gait speed and the Short Physical Performance Battery (SPPB) achieved lower AUROCs of 0.64–0.65. These findings suggest that ML approaches can outperform conventional, single-domain measures by integrating a broader array of predictors.

Scoping Review: ML-based Fall Risk Prediction Literature

ML models are inherently constrained by the quality and quantity of the data available to them. Therefore, as a milestone component of this thesis, a scoping review of 18 studies was conducted to investigate data sources for ML-based fall prediction. The review revealed considerable variation in input features and outcome definitions; a brief summary is provided here to contextualize the literature.

Input data for fall prediction was based on four main categories:

- **Self-reported questionnaires and administrative health data** were most common, including data such as demographics, comorbidities, medication use, activities of daily living (ADLs), and psychosocial health (Chen et al., 2023; Ikeda et al., 2022; Sharma et al., 2023; González-Castro et al., 2024).

- **Clinical performance tests** such as the Timed Up and Go (TUG), gait speed, SPPB, and the Performance-Oriented Mobility Assessment (POMA) were widely used (Cuaya-Simbro et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2019).
- **Wearable sensors** were included in several studies, particularly inertial measurement units (IMUs) placed on the trunk, sternum, or shoes, capturing gait and mobility patterns (Albites-Sanabria et al., 2024; Chakraborty & Sorwar, 2022; Chen et al., 2022).
- **Posturography data**, collected using force plates or robotic platforms, was less frequent but provided detailed sway and stability measures (Cella et al., 2020; Capodici et al., 2025).

Outcome definitions for classifying between fallers and non-fallers comprised:

- **Self-reported falls** was the most widely reported outcome, either retrospectively (Albites-Sanabria et al., 2024; Chakraborty & Sorwar, 2022) or prospectively through follow-up (Yang et al., 2019; González-Castro et al., 2024).
- **Clinician-assigned classifications** of fall risk was used by Roshdinenamet al., 2021 based on medical history and clinical evaluation of functional tests.
- **Healthcare utilization data** in the form of ICD-10 coded events (fall-related hospital admissions) was used by Sharma et al. (2023).

Overall, the scoping review shows that ML models for fall risk prediction have been tested with a wide range of inputs and outcomes, but with substantial variability across studies. The diversity of data highlights the flexibility of ML approaches but also reveals the challenge of establishing generalizable and reproducible models.

Gaps in the Literature

Although ML-based fall risk prediction shows promise, several gaps remain in the current literature. First, many studies continue to rely on a single type of data source – either large-scale registry data, which is practical for population-level analysis, or detailed but small-scale wearable IMU datasets – each capturing only one domain of fall risk. Second, evaluation practices are inconsistent: calibration and threshold selection are rarely reported, and many studies emphasize accuracy or area under the receiver operating curve (AUROC) while under-reporting other metrics more appropriate for imbalanced data, such as precision–recall curves and F1 scores (Sharma et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2022).

Third, interpretability is often limited. While some work has begun to apply methods such as SHAP to highlight key predictors (Ikeda et al., 2022; Albites-Sanabria et al., 2024), most studies provide little insight into how models arrive at their classifications, which restricts clinical trust and applicability. Finally, testing fall risk models across different geographic and healthcare contexts is essential for reproducibility and ensuring that predictions remain valid across diverse populations of older adults. However, there is an underrepresentation of ML-based fall risk studies in Denmark and the broader Nordic region, despite the existence of well-established preventive frameworks that collect large-scale data and provide a viable testing ground for investigating fall risk prediction.

The Danish Preventive Home Visit Context

Denmark was the first country to legislate nationwide Preventive Home Visits (PHVs) for older adults, introducing them in 1996 for those aged 80+ and extending coverage to everyone aged 75+ by 1998 (Sundhedsstyrelsen, 2006). Municipalities are legally required to offer PHVs, although participation is voluntary. The visits are most often carried out by district nurses but

may also involve other primary care professionals, reflecting a decentralized approach that allows municipalities to adapt the program locally.

Evidence from a Danish evaluative study shows that PHVs can reduce functional decline, lower the risk of hospitalization and nursing home admission, and support independence in older adults. Benefits are greatest when the visits are individualized and interdisciplinary, and they have been recognized as cost-effective by helping postpone costly institutional care, thereby embedding PHVs as a central pillar of Denmark's ageing policy (Vass et al., 2007).

PHVs have also been implemented in other Nordic countries. In Finland, a randomized controlled trial found that PHVs helped maintain health-related quality of life (HRQoL) over one year, as measured by the 15D instrument (mean difference = 0.015, $p = 0.028$) (Liimatta et al., 2019). While in a Swedish controlled trial, lower mortality was reported among older adults receiving PHVs compared to controls (27 vs. 48 deaths per 1,000; IRR = 1.79, $p < 0.05$) (Sahlen et al., 2006). Although these mortality and HRQoL benefits diminished once the programs ended, both studies demonstrate the potential of PHVs to support early detection and preventive action in ageing populations.

The HANC Study

The Healthy Ageing Network of Competence (HANC) study was established to augment Denmark's PHV program by embedding more comprehensive, standardized assessments into the existing framework (Tsai et al., 2021). Funded through the European Union's INTERREG 4a program (grant number 104–1.5 11, total budget €1.46M), the project was conducted in Odense Municipality between March 2013 and September 2014 in collaboration with the University of Southern Denmark (Interreg, 2023). Older adults aged 75+ who received PHV invitation letters

were also invited to take part in HANC, to integrate enhanced assessments within a real-world preventive care system.

Specifically, the HANC study expanded the traditional PHV model by including objective physical performance tests, cognitive screening, psychosocial and quality-of-life questionnaires, and continuous accelerometer-based activity monitoring. This multidimensional approach directly addresses gaps identified in previous ML studies, providing a unique opportunity to test multimodal, interpretable fall risk prediction models in a Danish context.

Aims and Objectives

The primary objective of this thesis is to develop and evaluate an interpretable machine learning model for fall risk prediction in community-dwelling older adults, using a multimodal dataset collected as part of the HANC study. The model integrates clinical, demographic, psychosocial, cognitive, and accelerometry-based data to classify individuals by fall risk. The secondary objectives are to:

- 1) Apply interpretability techniques, specifically SHAP analysis, to identify the most influential predictors of fall risk.
- 2) Assess real-world applicability by calibrating the model, optimizing thresholds, and commenting on how such a framework could support preventive screening in practice.

Methods

Study Design

This study is a retrospective cross-sectional analysis, using data that has already been collected at a single point in time, without prospective follow-up. Specifically, baseline data from the HANC study was used, which was conducted within Denmark's PHVs framework. Older adults aged 75+ who accepted participation completed in-home assessments of physical, cognitive, psychosocial, quality of life measures, and used a wrist-worn accelerometer for 7 consecutive days.

All procedures followed Danish Data Protection regulations. The study was approved by the Regional Scientific Ethical Committees for Southern Denmark (S-20120149), and all participants provided written informed consent.

Participant Characteristics

A total of 554 community-dwelling older adults (≥ 75 years) living in Odense participated in the HANC study. For the present analysis, we included the 382 participants who had complete outcome data, in the form of self-reported falls. Eligibility required a Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) score above 21, ensuring sufficient cognitive capacity to complete the assessments. At the time of participation, participants were not receiving any other municipal services such as rehabilitation.

Model Variables

The machine learning model used a curated subset of variables (hereafter referred to as *features*) from the HANC dataset, selected based on theoretical relevance to fall risk, availability, and data

completeness. These features encompassed demographic, physical activity, physical function, cognitive, psychological, and self-reported functional domains:

Input Features

1. Demographics and Anthropometrics

- Demographics: Age (years) and gender (female/male)
- Body mass index (BMI; kg/m²)

2. Physical Activity

- Average daily activity, mean counts per minute (CPM): Accelerometry data was collected using Actigraph GT3X/GT3X+ devices worn on the dorsal side of the dominant wrist for seven days. Data was considered valid if participants wore the device for ≥ 10 hours/day on at least 4 days.

Raw accelerometer data was initially processed by HANC researchers using ActiLife software (v6.4.11) and analyzed with the custom-made Propero software (University of Southern Denmark) to generate CPM in vector magnitude, based on 60-second epochs, as described in Tsai et al. (2021).

For this thesis, overall physical activity was operationalized as mean daytime CPM (06:00–23:00), calculated as the total activity counts divided by total wear time (minutes). Higher CPM values indicate greater overall physical activity volume.

3. Physical Function

- Short Physical Performance Battery (SPPB, Figure 1): Composite measure of 3 tests assessing lower-limb function:

- Balance score (0–4): Ability to maintain side-by-side, semi-tandem, and tandem stances.
- Gait speed (m/s): Average walking speed over a 3–4 m course.
- Chair-rise time (seconds): Time to complete five consecutive chair stands as quickly as possible, without using the arms.

Figure 1: Description and interpretation of Short Physical Function Battery (SPPB) scale (Tonet et al., 2023)

- Relative grip strength (kg/kg body weight): Mean of the highest recorded values from dominant and non-dominant hands, measured with a handheld Jamar dynamometer. Grip strength was normalized to body weight to account for body size differences, providing a relative measure of functional strength capacity rather than absolute force alone.

4. Health-related Quality of Life (HRQoL)

- 12-Item Short Form Health Survey (SF-12): Self-report questionnaire assessing eight health domains—physical functioning, role limitations due to physical health, bodily pain, general health, vitality, social functioning, role limitations due to emotional problems, and mental health. It produces two summary scores:
 - Physical Component Summary (SF-12 PCS)
 - Mental Component Summary (SF-12 MCS)
- EuroQol 5-Dimension Questionnaire (EQ-5D): A standardized measure of HRQoL comprising five domains—mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort, and anxiety/depression.
 - EQ-5D Index Value: Composite utility score derived from the five domains; higher scores indicate better overall perceived health.
 - EQ-5D Self-rated Health (SrH): Visual analog scale assessing current health status ranging from 0 (worst imaginable) to 100 (best imaginable) state.

Both SF-12 and EQ-5D capture HRQoL from different perspectives and play complementary roles. SF-12 differentiates physical and mental domains, offering insight into functional status, while the EQ-5D provides a concise utility index commonly used in health policy and economic evaluations. Although the two instruments show moderate correlation, they emphasize distinct aspects of perceived health, supporting their combined use in multi-dimensional analyses (Johnson & Pickard, 2000).

5. Cognitive Function

- Digit Symbol Substitution Test (DSST): Assesses processing speed, attention, and psychomotor coordination in a timed, writing-based task. Scored as the total number of symbols correctly completed, calculated as total symbols attempted minus errors.
- Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE): Widely used screening tool for global cognitive function. Assesses orientation, recall, attention, calculation, language, and visuospatial abilities. Scored out of 30, with lower scores indicating cognitive impairment.

6. Fatigue-based Measures

- Pittsburgh Fatiguability Scale (PFS): Self-report questionnaire assessing perceived fatigability for 10 items across two domains and each scored 0-50, with higher scores indicating more fatiguability.
 - Physical Score (PFS-PS)
 - Mental Score (PFS-MS)
- Total Avlund Score: Self-report measure of perceived tiredness during daily mobility tasks, with higher scores indicating more severe fatigue.

7. Activities of Daily Living (ADL) assessment: Self-report checklist evaluating the ability to perform basic and instrumental daily activities using an ordinal scale.

- Personal care tasks: Bathing, dressing, and toileting.
- Household and mobility tasks: Such as cooking, stair climbing, shopping, and managing household chores.

- Social engagement: Frequency of meeting with friends and family, and whether the participant lives alone or with others.

8. Fear of Falling (Falls Efficacy Scale-International “FESI”): Self-report questionnaire measuring concern of falling across 16 activities rated on a four-point ordinal scale (1 = not at all concerned to 4 = very concerned). The total FES-I score (range: 16–64) sums activities including:

- Personal self-care and household tasks: e.g., cleaning the house, getting dressed or undressed, preparing meals, taking a bath or shower.
- Indoor and outdoor mobility: e.g., walking up or down stairs, walking in the neighborhood, reaching for items above head height or from the ground, getting in or out of a chair.
- Challenging walking conditions: e.g., walking on slippery or uneven surfaces, walking in crowded places, walking up or down slopes.
- Social and community activities: e.g., visiting friends or relatives, going to shops, attending social events.

Outcome Definition

The primary outcome was self-reported falls within the past year. This was assessed using a supplementary question added as item 17 of the FES-I: *“Have you fallen in the past year?”* Responses were used to classify participants into two categories: fallers and non-fallers (in the past year). This binary classification was used as the outcome variable (“label”) for supervised ML model training and testing.

Data Preprocessing

The dataset was provided in an Excel file containing 554 participants and 392 features. All data was imported into a Jupyter Notebook in Python (version 3.12.5) for subsequent analyses.

Data Filtering

The primary outcome variable, self-reported falls in the past year, was missing for 172 out of 554 participants. Review of the HANC manual logs confirmed that these values were truly missing. As outcome data cannot be imputed, these participants were excluded, leaving 382 participants for analysis.

Features with more than 30% missing data were excluded to reduce the potential of excessive error in subsequent imputation, consistent with thresholding for data missingness exclusion used in previous fall risk prediction research (Ikeda et al., 2022). Additional variables were removed when they were not relevant to the research aim of fall risk prediction or represented overly granular measurements unlikely to improve model performance. As part of data cleaning, values coded as “9” in the HANC dataset, used to indicate missingness, were recoded as missing. After these initial filtering steps, the number of features in the HANC dataset was reduced from 418 to 64 features, which are listed above in the [Input Features](#) section.

Handling Missing Data (Multivariate Single Imputation)

Of the 65 retained features, 55 contained missing values. The variable with the highest proportion of missingness had missing data for 19.4% of participants (74 out of 382). Features were grouped as categorical (e.g., ADL and FES-I items, EQ-5D responses, gender) or numerical variables (e.g., grip strength, SPPB chair rise time, SF-12 scores). Missing values were addressed using multivariate single imputation via scikit-learn’s *IterativeImputer*, which uses the entire set of available features to estimate missing values to return a single imputed value (Scikit-learn.org,

n.d.). Three complementary distribution-based metrics were then applied to quantify imputation quality:

- **Normalized Wasserstein distance (W_%, “Earth Mover’s Distance”)**: Applied to numerical features as the primary distributional similarity metric, quantifying the “effort” required to transform one distribution into another. Distances were normalized by the observed range of each variable and expressed as percentages to enable comparison across features. Smaller values indicate closer alignment between observed and imputed data. This metric is particularly suitable for continuous variables and has been recommended for evaluating imputation quality when the true value is not available (Farjallah et al., 2024).
- **Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) statistic**: Also applied to numerical features to detect differences in the cumulative distribution function (CDF) between observed and imputed values. Values range from 0 to 1, with 0 indicating identical distributions. KS complements Wasserstein by being more sensitive to local differences and shifts in distribution shape, particularly around the median.
- **Hellinger distance (HD)**: Applied to categorical features to quantify the divergence between observed and imputed category distributions. Values range from 0 to 1, with values closer to 0 indicating greater similarity. Hellinger distance was selected for its suitability in comparing categorical distributions and its robustness to imbalanced or sparsely populated categories.

No universal reference thresholds exist for these distributional metrics; their interpretation is context-dependent and typically comparative, with lower values indicating better imputation

quality. In this study, the largest observed divergences were: Wasserstein distance = 1.32% for the EQ-5D index value, KS statistic = 6.77% for the Pittsburgh Fatigability Scale (mental score), and Hellinger distance = 0.017 for ADL8 (laundry). These relatively small values suggest minimal distortion in the distribution of imputed features. Representative visual comparisons are provided in [Appendix A](#).

Feature Reduction

Feature Engineering

Only one feature was engineered to reduce redundancy and improve interpretability. Grip strength was represented by a single variable, calculated as the average of the maximum recorded grip strength from the left and right hands, which was justified by the high shared variance between the two measures ($r^2 = 0.817$, $p < 0.001$). It was also normalized to body weight to account for body size differences and provide a relative measure of functional strength.

Multicollinearity Analysis

Multicollinearity occurs when two or more features convey overlapping information, which can reduce interpretability and unnecessarily increase model complexity with redundant features. Although many machine learning models tolerate collinearity without large losses in predictive accuracy, correlated predictors disperse feature importance and may slightly increase overfitting risk (Li-Ye Chan et al., 2022).

To identify redundant features, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was calculated for all remaining input features. According to Li-Ye Chan et al., 2022, a $VIF > 10$ often indicates multi-collinearity and in this study, a threshold of $VIF > 5$ was used for exclusion, indicating substantial redundancy. This led to the removal of several anthropometric features such as weight, waist circumference, and body fat percentage. SHAP feature importance analysis (described later) indicated that body

mass index (BMI) was the most informative among these correlated measures, and it was retained as the primary representative anthropometric variable.

Three features with VIF values above the exclusion threshold were retained due to strong domain relevance: (1) Total FES-I score (VIF = 26.6), which represents overall concern about falling. It is derived from 16 component items that were also included in the analysis, leading to multicollinearity; (2) Total SPPB score (VIF = 15.9), representing overall lower-limb function and derived from three component items that were also included; and (3) SPPB chair rise time, reflecting muscle power in a functional task. A correlation heatmap illustrating relationships between retained features is provided in [Appendix B](#).

ML Model Development

Model Selection: XGBoost

Following feature reduction, 46 features remained: 28 categorical and 18 numerical, across 382 participants. Categorical variables were one-hot encoded into 105 binary “dummy” variables, which were then combined with the numerical features to yield 123 total features for model training.

XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) is an ensemble method that constructs a series of decision trees, with each successive tree correcting the errors of its predecessors. It is particularly well-suited for fall risk prediction due to its ability to handle class imbalance and capture complex, non-linear relationships. In two comparable studies, XGBoost achieved superior performance over alternative models (Bae et al., 2025; Ikeda et al., 2022).

Model Evaluation Metrics

These were considered a priori to guide model training and ensure that the optimization process was aligned with the study's objectives. Metrics are categorized as threshold-dependent or threshold-independent.

Threshold-Dependent

These metrics require setting a classification threshold – in this study, the predicted probability at which a participant is classified as a faller or non-faller. Once classified, model predictions can be categorized as true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN), from which the following metrics are derived:

- $Recall \text{ (Sensitivity)} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
- $Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$
- $Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$
- $Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$
- $Balanced \text{ Accuracy} = \frac{Sensitivity + Specificity}{2}$
- $F1 = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$

Figure 2: Confusion matrix showing the distribution of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN). Darker shades of blue indicate a higher number of participants.

These metrics assess performance at a single chosen threshold, classifying participants as either positive (fallers) or negative (non-fallers), which can also be summarized in a confusion matrix (Figure 2). Ideally, most classifications should fall into true positives (TP, true fallers) and true negatives (TN, true non-fallers). For fall prevention purposes, minimizing false negatives (FN, “missed fallers”) is particularly important, as these represent individuals at risk who are not identified. This can be improved by increasing recall (sensitivity), though often at the cost of reduced precision, leading to more false positives (FP, “false alarms”). Both errors have implications for healthcare costs: FNs may result in preventable injuries and healthcare usage (e.g. hospitalizations and personal care services), while FPs may trigger unnecessary interventions (Sharma et al., 2023).

Threshold-Independent

These two metrics evaluate the model's ability to rank predictions without committing to a single classification threshold making the following particularly valuable during model training and hyperparameter optimization and a good representation of overall model discrimination performance (Capodici et al., 2025):

- AUROC (Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve) - Measures how well the model can distinguish between fallers and non-fallers across all thresholds. A value of 1 indicates perfect classification, while 0.5 suggests performance no better than chance.
- AUPRC (Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve) – Captures the trade-off between precision (avoiding FPs) and recall (avoiding FNs) across all thresholds. Unlike AUROC, which treats both classes equally, AUPRC places more emphasis on the positive class (fallers in this study), making it more informative for imbalanced datasets.

Threshold Selection

Applying a fall classification model in practice requires careful consideration of threshold selection, as this significantly affects the balance of FPs and FNs. Two common approaches considered were:

- *Youden's Index* selects the threshold that maximizes the sum of sensitivity and specificity. Geometrically, it corresponds to the point on the ROC curve farthest from the diagonal line of no discrimination (chance level).
- *F1 maximization* selects the threshold that yields the highest F1 score, defined as the harmonic mean of precision and recall. This method emphasizes the positive class by balancing false negatives and false positives.

Both methods were evaluated to determine the optimal classification threshold, with Youden's Index ultimately selected for the main analysis due to its more balanced performance across sensitivity and specificity.

Hyperparameter Search: Bayesian Optimization

In XGBoost, parameters are values learned automatically during training, with log-loss used in this study as the guiding objective. At each step, the algorithm builds a decision tree by selecting which features to split on (e.g., age, grip strength), choosing the cut-off values for those splits, and assigning predictions at the leaves – the endpoints of the tree where participants with similar characteristics are grouped. In contrast, hyperparameters are set before training and control the overall learning process, such as how deep the trees can grow, how many trees are built, and how strongly each update influences the model.

This study used Bayesian optimization to search for the best combination of hyperparameters. Unlike RandomSearch or GridSearch, which may test many unproductive combinations of hyperparameters and become computationally expensive, Bayesian optimization uses the results of previous trials to guide the next, improving search efficiency. The hyperparameters explored were:

- Number of boosting rounds – how many times the model updates itself.
- Maximum tree depth – how complex each decision tree can be.
- Learning rate – how much the model adjusts after each update.
- Subsample ratio – fraction of data rows used for each tree.
- Column sampling ratio – fraction of features used for each tree.
- Minimum loss reduction – threshold for splitting tree nodes.

- Class weight scaling – adjustment for class imbalance, as there are more non-fallers in the dataset.

Model performance was evaluated using five-fold stratified cross-validation. In each round, the model was trained on 80% of the data (four folds) and tested on the remaining 20% (one fold), ensuring that every participant was included in the test set exactly once. A total of 300 trials were run during hyperparameter optimization, with the goal of maximizing the area under the precision–recall curve (AUPRC), which was selected due to its suitability for imbalanced datasets – in this case, where non-fallers made up 70.4% of participants.

Final Model Training and Evaluation

The Bayesian optimization was run for 250 trials with different hyperparameter combinations. Whenever a model achieved a new best AUPRC, its performance was also evaluated at the Youden and F1-maximizing thresholds, reporting recall, precision, F1 score, AUROC, accuracy, and log loss. The final model was selected based not solely on AUPRC but on a balanced consideration of metrics, with particular emphasis on F1 score and log loss for their practical relevance. For evaluation, a confusion matrix was generated, and ROC and PRC curves were averaged across five cross-validation folds with shaded standard deviation bands. Threshold selection was further visualized using an F1-vs-Threshold plot, alongside recall and precision curves.

Calibration Evaluation

Calibration is a threshold-independent concept that assesses how well a model's predicted probabilities reflect the true likelihood of an outcome. For example, if 50% of individuals predicted to have a 50% fall risk actually fall, the probabilities are well-calibrated and carry real-world meaning. Deviations from this indicate miscalibration, where predicted risks do not align

with observed event rates. Importantly, good calibration does not guarantee strong performance on threshold-dependent metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, or specificity.

To quantitatively assess calibration, two metrics were computed: log-loss and Brier score. Log-loss, or cross-entropy loss, measures how well predicted probabilities align with observed outcomes, applying heavier penalties to predictions that are confident but incorrect. The Brier score captures the average squared difference between predicted probabilities and actual binary outcomes. Lower values for both metrics indicate better-calibrated and more informative probability estimates. Together, these metrics provide a summary of the overall quality of the model's probability estimates.

Visual tools were also used to examine calibration. A calibration curve was generated by grouping predicted probabilities into ten quantile-based bins of similar sample size, enabling direct comparison between predicted and observed event rates. In addition, a probability distribution histogram was plotted to show how risk scores were distributed across fallers and non-fallers, offering insight into how the classification threshold segments missed fallers and false alarms.

Model Interpretability: SHAP

Feature Importance (SHAP Summary Plot)

A “beeswarm” summary plot of the top 25 features was generated to show both the magnitude (importance) and direction (positive or negative influence) of their impact. Aggregated SHAP importance, combined with multi-collinearity analysis, was later used to reduce the feature set and retrain the model for improved efficiency and interpretability.

Feature Effects and Interactions (SHAP Dependence and Interaction Plots)

SHAP dependence plots show how changes in a feature's value relate to changes in its SHAP

value, making it easy to see that feature's overall effect on predictions. SHAP interaction plots build on this by showing how the impact of one feature can depend on the value of another. This can reveal patterns such as two features working together to strongly influence predictions (synergistic effects) or one feature's effect only becoming important under certain conditions (conditional effects).

Understanding Individual Predictions (SHAP Force Plots)

SHAP force plots — or “waterfall” plots — explain individual predictions by showing how each feature shifts the baseline prediction toward the final prediction. Features pushing toward fallers appear on one side, non-fallers on the other, with segment length proportional to the SHAP value. This offers a clear, intuitive breakdown of each prediction.

Results

Descriptive Statistics and Group Comparisons

Normality of continuous variables was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Grip strength and gait speed were normally distributed and therefore analyzed using independent-samples t -tests. Distribution of females, as a nominal variable, was compared using a χ^2 test. All other non-normally distributed continuous or ordinal variables were compared between fallers and non-fallers using Mann–Whitney U tests. Effect sizes were reported using the appropriate statistic for each test: Cohen's d for t -tests, rank biserial correlation (r) for Mann–Whitney U tests, and Cramer's V for χ^2 tests.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of fallers and non-fallers

Feature	Overall (n=382)	Fallers (n=113)	Non-fallers (n=269)	Effect Size	p-value
Age (years)	81 [79–84]	81 [79–84]	81 [79–84]	$r = 0.012$	0.848
Female	232 (60.7%)	67 (59.3%)	165 (61.3%)	$V = 0.019$	0.709
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.4 [23.6–29.1]	26.5 [23.7–29.8]	26.3 [23.5–28.7]	$r = 0.075$	0.249
Physical Activity (mean CPM/day)	1988 [1620–2426]	1888 [1496–2600]	1999 [1680–2381]	$r = 0.083$	0.198
Grip Strength (kg/kg bodyweight)	0.35 ± 0.11	0.32 ± 0.11	0.35 ± 0.11	$d = -0.298$	0.010*
FES-I (Total)	20 [17–24]	22 [18–28]	19 [17–23]	$r = 0.262$	<0.001*
SPPB Total	10 [8–11]	10 [7–11]	10 [8–11]	$r = 0.105$	0.102
SPPB Chair Rise Time (s)	12.6 [10.4–14.8]	12.9 [9.8–16.2]	12.6 [10.4–14.4]	$r = 0.062$	0.337
SPPB Gait Speed (m/s)	0.87 ± 0.25	0.86 ± 0.26	0.88 ± 0.25	$d = -0.077$	0.499
SPPB Balance Score	4 [3–4]	4 [3–4]	4 [3–4]	$r = 0.118$	0.028*
SF-12 PCS	44.7 [34.9–51.9]	40.9 [31.2–52.0]	45.4 [36.4–51.7]	$r = 0.118$	0.069
SF-12 MCS	57.8 [50.8–60.7]	57.5 [51.8–60.6]	57.8 [50.6–60.7]	$r = 0.006$	0.924
EQ-5D Index	0.86 [0.76–1.00]	0.84 [0.76–0.87]	0.86 [0.80–1.00]	$r = 0.214$	<0.001*
EQ-5D SrH	80 [60–90]	71 [55–88]	80 [67–90]	$r = 0.180$	0.005*
Avlund ADL Score	1 [0–2]	1 [0–2]	1 [0–2]	$r = 0.000$	0.995
Pittsburgh Fatigability (Physical)	14 [8–23]	16 [9–23]	13 [7–22]	$r = 0.080$	0.216
Pittsburgh Fatigability (Mental)	4 [0–11]	6 [0–12]	4 [0–10]	$r = 0.084$	0.189
DSST	25 [20–31]	24 [20–29]	26 [20–32]	$r = 0.100$	0.124
MMSE	29 [28–30]	29 [27–30]	29 [28–30]	$r = 0.066$	0.295

Note: Values are presented as *median [interquartile range]* for non-normally distributed variables and *mean ± standard deviation* for normally distributed variables.

*: $p < 0.05$, indicating a statistically significant difference between groups.

d: Cohen's *d*, *r*: Rank biserial correlation, *V*: Cramer's *V*

Fallers demonstrated significantly lower normalized grip strength ($d = -0.30$, $p = .010$) and poorer balance performance on the SPPB ($r = 0.118$, $p = .028$) compared with non-fallers. They also reported greater fear of falling on the FES-I ($r = 0.262$, $p < .001$) and poorer health-related quality of life on both the EQ-5D Index ($r = 0.214$, $p < .001$) and EQ-5D self-rated health ($r = 0.180$, $p = .005$). No other significant group differences were observed.

ML Model Training and Evaluation

An XGBoost classifier was trained to predict faller status using a stratified five-fold cross-validation framework. Log-loss was applied as the internal evaluation metric, while hyperparameters were optimized with Optuna across 300 trials. The optimization targeted the area under the precision–recall curve (AUPRC) as the primary objective, chosen for its suitability in imbalanced datasets. A summary of the optimization history is provided in [Appendix C](#).

Threshold-Independent Evaluation

Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) and precision–recall (PR) curves of the best-performing model are shown in Figure 3, with shaded bands representing ± 1 standard deviation across cross-validation folds. The model achieved an AUROC of 0.662 and an AUPRC of 0.473.

Figure 3: (a) Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve and (b) Precision–Recall (PR) curve for the final XGBoost model. The area under each curve (AUROC = 0.662, AUPRC = 0.473) is reported as a summary measure of model performance. A classification threshold of 0.29 is plotted on both curves, selected using Youden’s Index (see Threshold Selection). Shaded bands represent ± 1 standard deviation across five cross-validation folds.

It was trained using the following hyperparameters: $n_estimators = 128$, $max_depth = 7$, $learning_rate = 0.0146$, $subsample = 0.579$, $colsample_bytree = 0.773$, $gamma = 3.087$, and $scale_pos_weight = 1.11$.

Given that an AUROC of 0.50 and an AUPRC of 0.30 represent chance-level performance in this dataset, the model's scores indicate moderate discriminative ability. The AUROC reflects overall separation between fallers and non-fallers, while the AUPRC emphasizes performance on the minority faller class. Together, these metrics suggest that the model captured meaningful patterns from the available features.

Threshold Selection

Figure 4: Threshold selection using two methods: **(a)** F1 score, which optimizes the balance between precision and recall, and **(b)** Youden's Index, which maximizes the sum of sensitivity and specificity. The resulting thresholds (0.21 for F1 and 0.29 for Youden) reflect different priorities in classification trade-offs.

Two threshold selection methods were compared to determine the optimal cutoff for classifying fallers and non-fallers, as shown in Figure 4. The F1-maximizing threshold emphasized recall, resulting in a lower cutoff of 0.21 that reduced missed fallers but increased false positives. In contrast, the threshold identified by Youden's Index (0.29) provided a more conservative

tradeoff, with better specificity that reduced the number of false alarms. Thus, the Youden threshold was selected for the final evaluation, and its confusion matrix is presented below in the main Results section. The confusion matrix corresponding to the F1-maximizing threshold is included in [Appendix D](#) for comparison.

Threshold-based Evaluation

At the Youden-based threshold of 0.29, the model achieved the following performance metrics:

- Sensitivity (Recall): 0.64
- Specificity: 0.60
- Precision: 0.40
- F1 Score: 0.49
- Balanced Accuracy: 0.62

The confusion matrix for this threshold of 0.29 is shown in Figure 5. Of the 113 participants who reported a fall in the past year, 72 were correctly identified as fallers (true positives, 19%), while 41 were incorrectly classified as non-fallers (false negatives, 11%). Among the 269 participants who did not report a fall, 162 were correctly identified as non-fallers (true negatives, 42%), while 107 were incorrectly flagged as fallers (false positives, 28%).

Although the model captured a majority of fallers (sensitivity = 0.64), the number of false positives remained substantial, accounting for over a quarter (28%) of the total sample. This trade-off reflects the balance achieved by the Youden threshold – offering improved specificity relative to the F1-maximizing threshold, which produced a notably higher false positive rate.

Figure 5: Confusion matrix at the Youden-selected threshold of 0.29. Percentages represent the proportion of the total sample ($N = 382$). The model identified 72 of 113 fallers (true positives) and 162 of 269 non-fallers (true negatives), with 148 misclassifications (false positives and false negatives) overall.

Calibration Evaluation

The model's predicted probabilities yielded a log-loss of 0.572 and a Brier score of 0.193. While no universal evaluation thresholds exist for these metrics, lower scores indicate better calibration. Log-loss penalizes high-confidence errors and reflects how well the predicted probabilities align with observed outcomes; a score of 0.572 suggests acceptable but imperfect probabilistic accuracy.

The Brier score, which represents the mean squared difference between predicted probabilities and actual binary outcomes, also supports this assessment. The maximum Brier score for a non-informative model is determined by the outcome prevalence and is given by $Brier_{max} = p(1-p)$, where p is the proportion of positive case (fallers). Given that this dataset has a faller prevalence of 29.6%, the maximum Brier score is approximately 0.208. Thus, the model's Brier score of 0.193 is better than the non-informative baseline.

Figure 6: Calibration assessment of the final fall risk prediction model.

(a) Calibration curve based on 10 quantile bins (approximately equal-sized groups). The dashed diagonal line represents perfect calibration, while the shaded gray band indicates a ± 0.05 tolerance range. Red and green regions highlight areas of miscalibration. (b) Predicted probability histogram showing the distribution of fallers (blue) and non-fallers (gray) across probability bins. The vertical dashed line indicates the classification threshold of 0.29, selected using Youden's Index.

The calibration curve (Figure 6a) plots observed fall frequencies against predicted probabilities across 10 quantile bins of approximately equal size (~38–39 participants per bin). Notably, all points fall between probabilities of roughly 0.15 and 0.55, reflecting where the model concentrated most of its predictions – a pattern also evident in Figure 6b, with most predictions occurring between 0.20–0.30. While most bins in the calibration curve fall within the ± 0.05 tolerance band around the ideal diagonal, localized miscalibration is evident. The model was

underconfident (underpredicting fall risk) in the 0.20–0.35 range, contributing to missed fallers, and overconfident in the 0.35–0.50 range, leading to false alarms.

Figure 6b shows the predicted probability histogram, illustrating how risk scores are distributed across fallers (blue) and non-fallers (gray). The dashed vertical line at 0.29 represents the classification threshold selected via Youden's Index. The blue segments to the left of the threshold represent missed fallers, whereas the grey segments to the right of the threshold represent false alarms. This visually shows how moving the threshold to the left or right changes the tradeoff between sensitivity and specificity.

Feature Explainability: SHAP

Feature Importance: SHAP Summary “Beeswarm” Plot

Figure 7a shows the SHAP summary plot of the top 20 predictive features, ranked by their impact on the model's fall risk predictions. Each point represents a participant, with horizontal position reflecting the influence on predicted risk (SHAP value), and color indicating the raw feature value (blue = low, red = high). Features are ordered by overall importance, with those higher in the list having greater average impact.

Several features showed consistent directional effects: higher scores on the DSST (Digit Symbol Substitution Test), EQ-5D index, and SF-12 PCS (Physical Component Summary) were associated with reduced fall risk, while higher BMI and SF-12 MCS (Mental Component Summary) tended to increase risk. In contrast, some ADL-related variables, such as specific FES-I (Falls Efficacy Scale-International) items, showed more subtle or mixed patterns.

Figure 7: (a) SHAP summary plot of top 20 most predictive features, (b) Mean SHAP values for the top 20 features. ADL = activities of daily living, BMI (body mass index), CPM = counts per minute (from accelerometry), DSST (Digit Symbol Substitution Test), EQ-5D (EuroQol 5-Dimension Index), FES-I (Falls Efficacy Scale-International), MCS (Mental Component Summary), PCS (Physical Component Score), SF-12 (12-item Short Form Health Survey), SPPB (Short Physical Performance Battery)

Figure 7b presents the same features ranked by their mean absolute SHAP value, summarizing their average contribution to model predictions across all participants. The importance ranking emphasizes that fall risk is shaped by multiple domains – physical performance, perceived health, and psychological factors – rather than any single determinant.

Individual Feature Effects: SHAP Dependence Plots

To further explore how specific features influenced fall risk predictions, SHAP dependence plots were generated for three of the top 5 most important variables. These plots illustrate how the SHAP value (predicted impact on fall risk) changes with the raw value of each feature. Figure 8a demonstrates a U-shaped relationship between physical activity (measured by mean counts per minute per day) and predicted fall risk. Both low and high activity levels were associated with higher fall risk, with the lowest SHAP values observed at moderate CPM ranges.

Figure 8b shows a threshold-like pattern for Total FES-I where SHAP values begin to rise sharply above a score of ~ 27 . This aligns with established clinical cutoffs (Delbaere et al., 2010), where scores ≥ 28 indicate high concern about falling, and suggests that the model's behavior is consistent with known risk thresholds. Whereas figure 8c illustrates a clear negative linear association between normalized grip strength (kg per kg of body weight) and fall risk: as relative strength increases, the predicted risk of falling steadily decreases.

Figure 8: SHAP Dependence Plots of Selected Features.

(a) Physical activity (mean counts per minute/day), (b) fear of falling (Total FES-I score), and (c) normalized grip strength (kg/kg body weight)

Discussion

The primary aim of this thesis was to develop a ML model capable of distinguishing between fallers and non-fallers using a retrospective dataset – a goal that was achieved. The XGBoost model demonstrated moderate discriminatory performance and offered interpretability through SHAP analysis. In addition, this study explored the impact of classification thresholding, adding practical relevance to the findings.

Importantly, the model was built using a multimodal dataset – combining physical performance, accelerometry, and self-report data – which remains underutilized in the fall-risk prediction literature. By leveraging data from the Danish PHV system, this study provides insights that are directly relevant to the national public health context.

Comparison with Existing Models

Threshold-independent Performance

The model demonstrated moderate discriminative performance, with an AUROC of approximately 0.66 and an AUPRC of approximately 0.47 – both exceeding the random baselines of 0.50 and 0.30, respectively. These results indicate that the model provides meaningful discrimination between fallers and non-fallers, with AUPRC offering additional insight given the class imbalance.

Across existing ML-based fall-risk studies in community-dwelling older adults, AUROC values vary widely – from 0.55 in a study of first-time fallers among home care clients (Kuspinar et al., 2019) to 0.894 in a study using smart wrist-worn devices and the Resident Assessment Instrument–Home Care (RAI-HC) tool (Yang et al., 2019) – reflecting heterogeneity in sample size, data modality, and model architecture. AUPRC, reported less frequently, ranged from 0.10

using home health care assessments (Lo et al., 2019) to 0.20 in models predicting fall-related admissions (Sharma et al., 2023). Importantly, the interpretation of AUPRC must account for outcome prevalence; for example, Lo et al.'s AUPRC of 0.10 nearly doubled the random baseline of 0.051 in a dataset with 5.14% fallers, underscoring the importance of contextualizing precision–recall metrics in imbalanced settings.

Threshold-based Performance

At the selected threshold, the model achieved an F1 score of 0.49, with sensitivity of 0.64, specificity of 0.60, precision of 0.40, and balanced accuracy of 0.62. These moderate results indicate a reasonable ability to identify fallers while limiting false positives – an appropriate trade-off for municipal screening, where over- and under-identification both carry costs.

In the literature, studies using enriched datasets and advanced methods tend to report stronger performance. For example, Ikeda et al. (2022) used a large 3-year longitudinal cohort with added psychosocial variables and SMOTE-based resampling, achieving an F1 score of 0.89, accuracy of 0.88 and AUROC of 0.88. Similarly, Lockhart et al. (2021) leveraged wearable IMUs during gait assessment and reported 86.7% sensitivity, 80.3%, and accuracy of 81.6%. These models illustrate the gains possible with high-resolution sensor data or large, well-annotated datasets – but also demonstrate the practical trade-offs involved, as such models rely on resource-intensive inputs that may not be feasible for large-scale or routine use in public health settings

In contrast, models using routine or semi-structured data show performance levels closer to the present study. Makino et al. (2021), using questionnaires and simple sensors, reported sensitivity of 0.62, precision of 0.66, accuracy of 0.65, and AUROC of 0.70. Cuaya-Simbros et al. (2021) focused on osteoporotic women and used posturography with oversampling, achieving

sensitivity >0.81 , specificity >0.19 , precision of 0.97, and NPV of 0.66. By contrast, Lo et al. (2019) used routine EHR data and reported 62% balanced accuracy and 65.8% overall accuracy—almost identical to the current model’s performance.

Overall, this study’s model strikes a balance between interpretability, scalability, and acceptable performance. While it does not reach the top-end results of models using wearables or large national datasets, it performs within range of similarly structured approaches and demonstrates potential for use in community-based fall-risk screening.

Calibration Assessment

The model demonstrated moderate calibration performance, with a log-loss of 0.572 and a Brier score of 0.193. The calibration curve revealed areas of miscalibration, particularly in overconfident regions (leading to false positives) and underconfident zones (resulting in missed fallers). These findings indicate that post-hoc recalibration methods, such as Platt scaling or isotonic regression, could improve the reliability of predicted probabilities (NeptuneAI, 2023).

Prior studies have shown that ML models for fall-risk prediction tend to assign relatively low predicted probabilities across participants. Sharma et al. (2023) reported a Brier score of 0.082 and presented a highly-calibrated curve, with most predicted probabilities falling between 0% and 15%. Chen et al. (2023), using data from the China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Study, reported Brier scores ranging from 0.164 to 0.245 across five models. Heo et al. (2023) also used five models, showing calibration plots for fall-related injury outcomes with predicted probabilities clustered between 5% and 30%.

This consistent trend toward low predicted risk likely reflects two factors: first, the subtle and multifactorial nature of fall-risk signals, which may limit model confidence; and second, the

class imbalance common across these studies – as in the current study – where non-fallers make up the majority and thus drive the overall probability distribution downward. The distribution of predicted risks in this study, as shown in the calibration plots and prediction histogram, is consistent with these prior findings.

Overall, calibration metrics remain underreported in the fall prediction literature, hindering the clinical interpretability of model outputs. Without these metrics, it is difficult to assess how well predicted probabilities reflect true risk – limiting trust and potential integration into decision-making workflows.

Model Interpretability (SHAP Analysis)

The top features contributing to fall-risk prediction in this model included a combination of physical activity levels (e.g., mean counts per minute), physical performance tests (SPPB chair rise time, grip strength), and self-report questionnaires (FES-I, SF-12, DSST, EQ-5D). This highlights the importance of using a multi-domain dataset. SHAP dependence plots revealed that the model captured non-linear patterns – for example, a U-shaped relationship between the most important feature, physical activity, and fall risk, where moderate levels were associated with lower risk.

SPPB chair rise time ranked as the second most important feature, reflecting the relevance of lower extremity strength and power. Similar importance for chair stand tests has been reported in other studies (Ikeda et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2025; Makino et al., 2021). Concern about falling, measured by Total FES-I, ranked third and was also identified as a key predictor in Ikeda et al. (2022), consistent with broader evidence supporting fall history as the strongest single predictor (Chen et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2019; Lin et al., 2025).

Measures of health-related quality of life (EQ-5D and SF-12) also featured prominently in the model, echoing findings from SHAP- and information gain-based feature rankings in other studies (Ikeda et al., 2022; Bae et al., 2025). Cognitive status, particularly processing speed and attention assessed via DSST, ranked sixth in this model. However, MMSE, which evaluates global cognitive function, ranked low (20th), which contrasts with other studies where MMSE was more predictive (Yang et al., 2019; Bae et al., 2025; Chen et al., 2023).

Unexpectedly, some variables commonly found predictive in the literature ranked lower in this study. Age, a top feature in other models (Ikeda et al., 2022; Bae et al., 2025; Lin et al., 2025), did not rank highly here, although "age at retirement" emerged as a relevant proxy ("adl22" in Figure 7). Gender ranked lowest amongst all 47 features, whereas another study identified female gender as a key risk factor, especially in urban settings (Lin et al., 2025).

Finally, certain predictors not collected in the HANC dataset, such as polypharmacy (Cella et al., 2019; Lin et al., 2025) and depressive symptoms (Chen et al., 2023), have shown strong predictive value in other studies. Given the multifactorial nature of falls, incorporating features from these additional domains could improve model performance in future iterations.

Implications for Practice and Policy

This study demonstrates that routinely collected municipal health data, such as physical performance metrics, accelerometry, and self-report questionnaires, can be leveraged to develop a semi-automated decision-support tool for identifying older adults at elevated risk of falling. By aligning with the structure of Denmark's preventive home visit (PHV) framework, the model provides a multidimensional assessment of fall risk that can support, but not replace, clinical decision-making. Its practical use lies in complementing PHV assessments by flagging

individuals for further evaluation or intervention, using features already embedded in standard practice.

Classification Threshold Selection

A critical aspect of real-world implementation is threshold selection. While this study used the Youden Index to identify an optimal threshold, practical cutoffs should be set by municipalities or health authorities based on local resource constraints and the relative costs of false positives (unnecessary interventions) and false negatives (missed fallers) (Sharma et al., 2023).

Yet, despite the importance of this trade-off, most fall prediction studies – including high-performing models using threshold-based metrics such as those by Ikeda et al. (2022), Bae et al. (2025), and Chen et al. (2023) – do not explain how classification thresholds were selected or provide justification based on clinical or economic reasoning. For example, Chen et al. (2023) implemented thresholds ranging from 0.209 to 0.49 based on different models, but did not offer methodological insight into how these values were determined. This lack of transparency limits the reproducibility, interpretability, and practical applicability of such models in healthcare settings.

Parallels with the Danish WIPP-360 Preventive Care Model

A useful comparison can be made to Denmark's existing *Welfare Innovation in Primary Prevention* (WIPP-360) system, which is a municipally implemented program designed to enable early detection of frailty among older adults. The WIPP-360 model combines simple physical performance tests with a structured digital questionnaire administered to citizens aged 65 and older. This questionnaire assesses various dimensions such as daily functioning, self-rated health,

and overall well-being. Based on these inputs, individuals are triaged into green, yellow, or red categories according to their support needs.

As of 2024, the system had already identified more than 1,500 particularly vulnerable older adults using this hybrid screening and triage approach (Kousgaard, 2024). Those classified in the red category may be offered targeted preventive home visits or referrals to rehabilitation services, while lower-risk individuals may simply be monitored.

A machine learning–based fall-risk model, such as the one presented in this thesis, could be integrated into a similar triage framework by using predicted risk probabilities to inform the allocation of preventive interventions and improve resource efficiency. Furthermore, post-hoc calibration methods – such as Platt scaling or isotonic regression – could be used to better align predicted probabilities with observed outcomes over time (NeptuneAI, 2023), enhancing model trustworthiness and applicability in real-world settings.

Implementation Considerations

The model’s use of modifiable predictors, such as SPPB and grip strength, enhances its potential utility in community-based screening and prevention programs (Ikeda et al., 2022; Bae et al., 2025). These variables are responsive to interventions like exercise and physiotherapy, making the model well-suited for targeting fall-risk factors that can be actively addressed. As such, it supports a precision prevention approach, directing services to those most likely to benefit.

Implementing this model in practice would require integration with existing electronic health records or municipal IT systems to automate prediction workflows. Periodic retraining may be needed as population characteristics shift or new data become available (Sharma et al., 2023).

Clear communication of outputs to clinicians and decision-makers is essential, particularly if

predictions influence care planning. While not yet ready for clinical deployment, the model offers a promising foundation for scalable, interpretable, and data-driven fall-risk stratification in municipal healthcare settings.

Strengths, Limitations, and Future Directions

Strengths

A key strength of this study is its use of a multimodal dataset integrating physical performance tests, accelerometer-derived activity measures, and self-reported questionnaires to develop a ML model for fall-risk prediction. The methods were transparently reported, including preprocessing, threshold tuning, and evaluation with confusion matrices, calibration curves, Brier score, and log-loss – addressing key gaps in reproducibility and methodological rigor often missing in related studies. Moreover, by leveraging data aligned with Denmark’s preventive home visit (PHV) framework, the study demonstrates real-world relevance and potential scalability for municipal fall-prevention initiatives.

Limitations

This study’s cross-sectional design limits its ability to predict future falls, and neither external nor temporal validation was conducted – both of which are essential to assess generalizability to unseen data, particularly in real-world settings (Sharma et al., 2023). The sample size (N=382) was relatively small, which may restrict the model’s robustness. Although a random forest model was initially tested, only XGBoost was optimized, whereas it remains unknown if alternative algorithms would have resulted in significant performance gains. Fall outcomes were based on self-report, without information on injury severity or fall-related healthcare use, which limits the model’s capacity to distinguish between low- and high-consequence fall events. Additionally,

data on recurrent falls was available but not leveraged to create a separate class, which could have enabled more nuanced risk stratification. Given its moderate predictive performance and limited validation, the model is not yet suitable for clinical deployment.

Future Directions

Future work should prioritize testing the model on larger and more diverse datasets to improve generalizability. Incorporating temporal and external validation would better simulate real-world deployment and evaluate performance across time and populations. Additional model architectures – such as LightGBM and neural networks – should be explored to assess whether more complex classifiers yield improved performance. Introducing a third class (e.g., recurrent fallers) or using more specific outcome definitions, such as fall-related healthcare utilization or injury severity, could enhance clinical relevance and allow for more granular risk stratification, especially within Danish municipal prevention frameworks. Finally, applying post-hoc calibration methods, including Platt scaling or isotonic regression, along with post-calibration adjustments, may further increase the reliability and interpretability of predicted probabilities in clinical decision-making contexts.

Conclusion

This thesis demonstrated the feasibility of using machine learning to predict fall risk among community-dwelling older adults based on multimodal data collected within Denmark's preventive home visit (PHV) framework during the HANC study. By integrating physical performance measures, accelerometry, self-report questionnaires, and health-related quality-of-life indicators, the developed XGBoost model achieved moderate predictive performance and offered meaningful interpretability through SHAP analysis. Although the model does not yet

reach the performance levels of large-scale models, it compares favorably with similarly structured approaches and relies on routinely collected, scalable inputs.

Key contributions include transparent reporting of evaluation metrics, including confusion matrices, calibration and threshold selection – addressing common gaps in the fall-risk prediction literature. The model's reliance on modifiable risk factors supports its potential use as a decision-support tool to guide targeted interventions in municipal care settings. However, limitations such as the cross-sectional design, small sample size, and lack of external validation constrain immediate clinical application.

Future research should focus on larger-scale datasets, prospective validation, exploring alternative model architectures, refine fall outcome definitions and investigate multi-tiered classification schemes to enhance clinical utility. Overall, this study lays a foundation for the development of interpretable, real-world machine learning tools for fall-risk stratification in ageing populations, contributing to the shift toward data-driven precision prevention in public health.

Appendix

Appendix A: Multivariate Single Imputation Graphs

Figure 9: Comparison of observed (blue) and imputed (red) distributions for three representative features with the highest divergence under each imputation quality metric. **(a)** EQ-5D Index Value (Wasserstein distance = 1.32%), **(b)** Pittsburgh Fatigue Score – Mental (KS statistic = 6.77%), and **(c)** ADL8 – Laundering (Hellinger distance = 0.017). Green dotted lines in panels a and b represent the locations of imputed values. Red bar labels in panel c show the count of imputed responses for each category.

Figure 9 shows a visual comparison of observed and imputed data for three variables, each selected because it showed the highest divergence on one of the distributional similarity metrics. For the two numerical variables (panels a and b), the blue and red density curves represent the original and imputed data, and the green vertical lines show where imputation was applied. The spread of these green lines highlights the regions most affected by missing data. Despite small differences in the tails, the overall shapes of the curves are similar, suggesting that the imputed values fit well into the original distributions.

In the categorical example (panel c), the bar heights show the relative frequency of each response, and numbers inside the red bars indicate how many values were imputed. The imputed distribution closely follows the original, with only small differences in less common categories. Overall, these plots visually support the quantitative metrics reported and suggest that imputation introduced minimal distortion.

Appendix B: Pearson Correlation Heatmap of Input Features

Figure 10 presents the Pearson correlation heatmap of the retained input features, highlighting several notable patterns. As expected, strong intercorrelations were observed among the 16 FES-I items (fes1–fes16), reflecting their shared conceptual focus on fear of falling. Despite high multicollinearity, these items were retained to preserve granularity, while the total FES-I score was included for its clinical interpretability and importance (VIF = 26.6).

Similarly, components of the Short Physical Performance Battery (SPPB), such as gait speed, balance, and chair rise time, showed strong correlations with each other and with the total SPPB score (VIF = 15.9), which was also retained for domain relevance. Other observed relationships included high correlations between total Pittsburgh Fatigability Scale physical and mental scores,

as well as between general health indicators like ADL1 (self-rated health) and the EQ-5D self-rated health, which assess similar constructs.

Figure 10: Heatmap showing pairwise Pearson correlations between all 48 numeric and ordinal input features. Strong positive correlations are shown in red, and negative correlations in blue.

Grip strength and gender showed moderate correlation, consistent with expected biological differences. Aside from the two retained features with high VIFs, all others fell below the exclusion threshold of 5. Whereas several anthropometric variables were excluded due to low SHAP-based feature importance. Overall, the heatmap confirms domain-consistent groupings and assisted with the feature reduction strategy aimed at minimizing dispersion of importance across redundant predictors.

Appendix C: Hyperparameter Search – Bayesian Optimization History

During hyperparameter optimization, the area under the precision-recall curve (AUPRC) improved from an initial baseline of 0.43 to a best score of 0.47, reflecting meaningful gains in model performance. Although performance gains plateaued over time, the process confirms the value of iterative tuning. A total of 300 trials were conducted using Bayesian optimization, balancing exploration and exploitation to refine the model's predictive ability.

Figure 11: Bayesian optimization history of AUPRC across 300 hyperparameter tuning trials. Each point represents the AUPRC score for a given trial, while the red step line tracks the best score achieved up to that point.

Appendix D: Threshold-based Evaluation – F1-Optimized Threshold

Figure 12: Confusion matrix at the F1-optimized threshold of 0.21. Percentages represent the proportion of the total sample ($N = 382$). The model correctly identified 102 of 113 fallers (true positives) and 86 of 269 non-fallers (true negatives), resulting in 194 misclassifications (false positives and false negatives) overall.

- Sensitivity (Recall): 0.90
- Specificity: 0.32
- Precision: 0.36
- F1 Score: 0.51
- Accuracy: 0.49

Figure 12 presents the confusion matrix at the threshold that maximized the F1 score (0.51). This setting yielded high sensitivity (0.90), meaning most fallers were correctly identified, but at the cost of low precision (0.36) and a large number of false alarms. This reflects a threshold strategy

that prioritizes minimizing missed fallers over avoiding unnecessary interventions. Such an approach may be appropriate in clinical or preventive settings where the consequences of missing a fall risk are severe, and the cost or burden of the intervention is low. This trade-off underscores the need to tailor threshold selection to the practical realities and priorities of the intended use case.

Appendix E: Conversion of SHAP Value to Probability

SHAP values from XGBoost are expressed in log-odds and can be added across features to obtain a total SHAP value for each individual. Applying the logistic (sigmoid) function to the total SHAP value converts it into predicted probability, providing an intuitive way to interpret model output. Figure 13 illustrates this conversion, giving a direct sense of how additive SHAP contributions translate into fall risk probability.

Figure 13: Logistic transformation of SHAP values (log-odds) into predicted probabilities. The dashed grey line marks the model baseline (50% probability, SHAP = 0), while the dashed blue line shows the Youden threshold (29% probability, SHAP \approx -0.90). The model indicates higher fall risk with increasing SHAP values and vice versa.

The curve is steepest between SHAP values of roughly -2 and 2 , where the relationship is almost linear and small changes have the greatest effect on probability. The baseline (SHAP = 0) corresponds to a 50% predicted probability, while the Youden threshold (29%) maps to SHAP ≈ -0.90 . Together, these markers highlight how SHAP values relate to clinically meaningful decision points and provide an intuitive framework for interpreting the model's predictions.

Appendix F: Individual Participant Prediction – SHAP Waterfall Plot

Figure 14 illustrates for the model arrived at an individual prediction using a SHAP waterfall plot. It shows a breakdown of feature contributions for a single participant who was correctly classified as a faller.

In this plot, the model starts from a base value, which represents the average model output (in log-odds) across all participants in the training set. From this starting point, each feature's SHAP value is added or subtracted depending on whether it increases or decreases the predicted fall risk. These SHAP values reflect the magnitude and direction of each feature's contribution for that specific participant.

The sum of these SHAP values gives the final model output (also in log-odds), which is then passed through the sigmoid function to produce the final probability of fall risk. This helps interpret not just the prediction itself, but how the model weighed various health, performance and functional measures for the individual. This level of transparency can support better understanding and potential clinical trust in the model's conclusions.

Figure 14: SHAP waterfall plot for a correctly predicted faller (Participant 18). Each bar shows how individual features contributed to the model's predicted fall risk, starting from the base value ($E[f(x)] = -0.883$) and summing to the final prediction ($f(x) = -0.155$). Participant was correctly predicted as a faller.

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